

Assessment of Knowledge Gap and Risk of Zoonosis among Abattoir Workers in Ebonyi North Senatorial District, Ebonyi State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Background: Zoonotic diseases are important public health problems worldwide. They are detrimental to animal health resulting to great economic losses as well as a threat to the national food security and human health. This study assessed the knowledge gap and risk of acquisition of zoonotic diseases among abattoir workers in Ebonyi North Senatorial District, Ebonyi State, Nigeria.

Methodology: This was a descriptive cross-sectional study. A total of 347 respondents were recruited through cluster sampling technique. Information on knowledge and preventive measures of zoonosis among the abattoir workers was obtained using a semi-structured interviewer-administered questionnaire. Statistical analyses (proportions, means with standard deviations, chi-square test) were carried out using with IBM-SPSS version 26 software.

Results: The mean age of the respondents was 33.8±10.7years and 67.7% were males. A total of 73.5% respondents were found to have adequate knowledge of zoonosis. Only 36.5% practiced effective preventive measures regarding zoonosis and only 42.4% always used personal preventive equipment during work. The barriers to the use of personal protective equipment when available were inconvenience (42.5%) and perception of low risk to the hazards (28.5%).

Conclusion: The knowledge of zoonosis in this study was high but this high level of knowledge did not translate to consistent practice of effective preventive measures against zoonotic diseases. We therefore recommend further health education, training and re-training of the abattoir workers in Ebonyi North Senatorial District to enable them practice effective prevention measures and to reduce the risk of contracting zoonosis.

Key Words: Zoonosis, Knowledge, Preventive practices, Abattoir workers.

Introduction

Zoonotic diseases are important public health problems worldwide. They are detrimental to animal health which results to great economic losses due to reduced production of meat, milk and wools. They also pose a threat to the national food security and to the achievement of sustainable development goals on eradicating extreme hunger and poverty. Emerging zoonotic diseases (Lassa fever, Anthrax, etc.) are also a threat to human existence. The magnitude and true public health significance of zoonosis is largely unknown because of lack of global data on the prevalence of entire zoonosis.¹⁻⁴

Man acquires the infection as a result of his occupation, proximity or contact with infected animals, animal products or wastes. However, certain groups such as abattoir workers, shepherds, veterinarians and pet owners are at higher risk of contracting zoonosis than the general populations. In Nigeria, abattoir workers constitute a major group at risk of contracting occupational zoonosis due to the close contact existing between them and animals/tissues during slaughter and processing.⁵ Thus working conditions and habits (behavioral risks) are important factors that aid the spread of zoonosis.

Abattoir work is associated with health hazards that could result in occupational diseases or may aggravate the existing ill health of non-occupational origin,⁶ with zoonosis gradually becoming a major global threat to public health and animal welfare.^{7,8} Occupational infections mostly contracted by abattoir workers could be caused by iatrogenic or by transmissible agents, including viruses, bacteria, fungi, and parasites; and their toxins.⁶

The fact that most zoonoses are usually insidious and that it is practically impossible to totally prevent contact with animals, animal products or waste further underscores the need for a knowledgeable public, especially the high risk populations on its cause, mode of transmission, clinical features and methods of prevention and control. Thus the study was designed to assess the knowledge gap and risk of acquisition of zoonotic diseases among abattoir workers in Ebonyi North Senatorial District, Ebonyi State, Nigeria.

Methodology

Study Setting

The study was done in Ebonyi North Senatorial District of Ebonyi State Nigeria. Ebonyi State is one of the most agrarian of the states in Nigeria made up of predominantly farmers. The State is blessed with moist land for growing varieties of cash and food crops such as rice, yam, cassava and cocoyam. Ebonyi State is made up of three senatorial districts which are Ebonyi North, Ebonyi Central and Ebonyi South districts. It has 13 Local Government Areas, of which 4 make up Ebonyi North Senatorial District. These include Abakaliki, Ebonyi, Izzi and Ohaukwu Local Government Areas. There are four major abattoirs in Ebonyi North Senatorial District located in Meat market, Gariki, Kpirikpiri and Ezzangbo.

Study Design

The study used cross-sectional descriptive in design.

Study population

The study population comprised of all the workers in the four major abattoirs in Ebonyi North Senatorial District who had worked in the slaughter house for at least half a year.

Sample size determination

A sample size of 347 was determined using an appropriate formula for estimating minimum sample size for descriptive studies ($n = Z\alpha^2 pq/d^2$).⁹ The following parameters were used to compute the sample size for the study: standard normal deviate ($Z\alpha$), 1.96 at 95% confidence interval, margin of error (d) of 0.05 and prevalence (p) is the level of knowledge of occupational hazards from a previous study which was 10%,¹⁰ and q is 1-p.

Sampling technique

Cluster sampling technique was used for the selection of respondents. The list of the major abattoirs in Ebonyi North Senatorial District was obtained from Ebonyi State Ministry of Environment and included: Meat market, Gariki, Kpirikpiri and Ezzangbo. All the clusters were included in the study. The respondents selected from each cluster were proportionate to the sizes of the clusters and were as follows: Meat market

86 (24.8%), Gariki 69 (19.9%), Kpirikpiri 80 (23%) and Ezzamgbo 112 (32.3%).

Study Instrument and method of data collection

Interviewer administered semi-structured questionnaire with open and close ended questions adapted from a previous study was used to collect data from eligible respondents.¹¹ The questionnaire contained relevant questions on socio-demographic characteristics, knowledge and prevention of zoonosis and data were collected using trained research assistants.

Data management and analysis

Data were analyzed using IBM SPSS version 26 software. Descriptive statistics were used to present proportions, means and standard deviations. Cross tabulations with chi-square test were made with level of statistical significance set at $p < 0.05$. In the study, scoring and categorization system were adapted from previous study.¹¹ The level of knowledge of respondents was termed adequate when at least 70% of responses were correct and inadequate when less than 70% of responses were correct. The perception to occupational hazards of respondents was termed positive when the responses were known to be positive. The risk of acquisition of zoonotic diseases among the respondents was determined by their level of practice of preventive measures.¹¹

Ethical Considerations

The ethical approval for the study was obtained from University Research Ethics Committee (UREC), Directorate of Research, Innovation and Commercialization (DRIC) of Ebonyi State University Abakaliki (EBSU/DRIC/UREC/VOL 06/056). The purpose of the surveys was explained to the management of the abattoir facilities and permission was granted. Individuals' informed consent was obtained from the respondents. They were assured of confidentiality of the information provided.

Results

Three hundred and forty-seven workers in the abattoirs were sampled. These played different roles in the abattoir ranging from 143 (41.2%) meat sellers, 61 (17.6%) who slaughtered, 79

(22.8%) who butchered for sellers and 30 (8.6%) live animal retailers. Respondents had a mean age of 33.8 ± 10.7 years with more males (67.7%) than females. Most respondents (263; 75.8%) had either a primary or secondary school education. The vast majority of respondents (331; 95.4%) had spent 2 years and more in the industry (Table 1). Majority of the respondents (255; 73.5%) had adequate knowledge of zoonosis. Only 43.2% of the respondents knew that some diseases can be transmitted from humans to animals (Table 2). This study showed that 85.6% of the abattoir workers had positive perception of hazards (Table 3).

Those that practiced effective preventive measures regarding zoonosis were only 36.5%. The study revealed that only 42.4% always used personal preventive equipment during work. The barriers to the use of personal protective equipment when available were inconvenience (42.5%) and perception of low risk to hazard (28.5%) (Table 4).

Table 1 : Socio-demographic characteristics of respondents

Variables	n=347 Freq.(%)
Abattoir facility	
Meat market	86(24.8)
Gariki	69(19.9)
Kpirikpiri	80(23.0)
Ezzamgbo	112(32.3)
Age(years)	
	34(9.8)
21-30	109(31.4)
31-40	120(34.6)
	84(24.2)
Mean age ± SD	
Sex	33.8±10.7
Male	
Female	235(67.7)
Marital status	112(32.3)
Single	
Married	145(41.8)
Educationa l status	202(58.2)
None	
Primary	34(9.8)
Secondary	103(29.7)
Tertiary	160(46.1)
Role in the abattoir	50(14.4)
Slaughter	
Seller	61(17.6)
Retailer	146(41.2)
Butcher	30(8.6)
Others	79(22.8)
Duration of service in yrs	34(9.8)
½-1	
2-5	16(4.6)
	177(51)
Mean year of service	154(44.4)
±SD	7.3±6.9

Table 2: Respondents' basic knowledge of zoonosis

**multiple responses allowed
n=347;

Basic Knowledge	Correct Response Freq.(%)	Wrong Response Freq.(%)
Some diseases can be transmitted from animals to humans	305(87.9)	42(12.1)
Some diseases can be transmitted from humans to animals	150(43.2)	197(56.8)
Mode of transmission of zoonosis include**		
Repeated contact with infected animals	240(69.2)	107(30.8)
Eating infected meat	303(87.3)	44(12.7)
Infected dairy products	248(71.5)	99(28.5)
Through skin and hide	160(46.1)	187(53.9)
Animal bite	255(73.5)	92(26.5)
Breathing in of infectious aerosols/droplets	243(70.0)	104(30.0)
Contamination with excreta	301(86.7)	46(13.3)
Undercooked meat (consumption of raw meat)	282(81.3)	65(18.7)
Via cuts and o ther forms of injuries (open wounds)	244(70.3)	103(29.7)
Splashes of blood and other body fluids eye and other mucous membrane	175(50.4)	172(49.6)
Those at risk of contracting zoonosis are**		
Butchers	279(80.4)	66(19.6)
Livestock breeders	201(57.9)	146(42.1)
Abattoir workers	227(65.4)	120(34.6)
Veterinarians	114(32.9)	233(67.1)
Consumers	216(62.2)	131(37.8)
Those involved in tanning and hiding of skin	115(33.1)	232(66.9)
Researchers and pet owners	121(34.9)	226(65.1)
Common clinical features of zoonosis**		
Fever	235(67.7)	112(32.3)
Vomiting/diarrhea	247(71.2)	100(28.8)
Skin rashes/itching	188(54.2)	159(45.8)
Abdominal discomfort	226(65.1)	121(34.9)
Cough	169(48.1)	178(51.3)
Most zoonosis can be treated	300(86.5)	47(13.5)
Level of basic knowledge of zoonosis	255(73.5)	
Adequate	92(26.5)	
Inadequate		

Table 3: Perception of occupational hazards in abattoir among respondents

Variables	Freq (%) (n=347)
Hazard /health problems associated with abattoir work**	
Cut	331(95.4)
Needle stick injuries	269(77.5)
Back injuries	265(76.4)
Severe injuries/deep laceration	270(77.8)
Scalding/burning	179(51.6)
Accidents	221(63.7)
Noise exposure	207(59.7)
Contaminated air (air pollution)	256(73.8)
Animal contact (injury by animals)	255(73.5)
Slippery surfaces (slippery floor)	274(79.0)
Work stress	311(89.6)
Electric shock	76(21.9)
Offensive/unpleasant odour	258(74.4)
Those responsible for occupational safety**	
Employers (management)	290(83.6)
Employees	207(59.7)
Government	172(49.6)
Those to be contacted for occupational health and safety**	
Doctor	277(79.8)
Supervisor	177(51.0)
Colleagues	88(25.4)
Trade unions	126(36.3)
Level of perception	
Positive	297(85.6)
Negative	50(14.4)

**Multiple responses allowed

Table 4: Preventive measures practiced by respondents

Variables	Freq (%) (n=347)
Had general safety training at work	
Yes	158(45.5)
No	189(54.5)
Ever used personal protective equipment	
Yes	311(89.6)
No	36(10.4)
Frequency of use of protective devices (n=311)	
Always	132(42.4)
Sometimes	179(57.6)
Reasons for not always using protective devices (n=179)	
Non-availability	30(16.8)
Not necessary	51(28.5)
Inconvenient	76(42.5)
Can't afford it	22(12.2)
Willingness to use personal protective equipment (PPE) if available (n=30)	
Yes	24(80.0)
No	4(13.3)
Undecided	2(6.7)
Had been subjected to medical examination before commencement of employment/work in this facility	47(13.5)
Yes	300(86.5)
No	
Undergoes routine (periodic) medical examination	82(23.6)
Yes	265(76.4)
No	
Ever vaccinated in relation to this work to prevent diseases	113(32.6)
Yes	265(76.4)
No	
Ever had chemoprophylaxis in relation to this work to prevent diseases	122(35.2)
Yes	225(64.8)
No	
Practice of preventive measures	126(36.3)
Practiced effective measures	221(63.7)
Practiced ineffective measures	

Discussion

This study showed that majority of the respondents had adequate knowledge of zoonosis. This is similar to findings from a study in Sokoto metropolis which showed that seven in ten of the study participants had adequate knowledge about zoonosis.¹⁰ This was also similar to another study in Ebonyi State which showed good knowledge level of good hygiene practices against zoonosis.¹⁶ This was, however, in contrast to another study which showed that a third knew about anthrax being a common zoonotic infection.¹² A study in Johannesburg also showed that about one-third had knowledge of meat safety practices.¹³ Another study in Ethiopia showed that almost two out of five had good knowledge of meat safety.¹⁴ However, in the present study more than two out of every five of the respondents knew that diseases can be transmitted from humans to animals. Similar observations were also seen in studies in Sokoto and in Malaysia.^{7,10} High level of educational among the respondents can be utilized in training and re-training, inter-sectorial sensitization and awareness creation forum to promote effective control practices.

There was a high perception of occupational hazards in the slaughter house among abattoir workers. In spite of the high positive perception and the fact that the vast majority were aware of the existence of zoonosis in the index study, the practice of the respondents was poor as only two in five always used personal preventive equipment (PPE) during work.

Findings from this study showed that almost two out of five respondents' preventive practices was considered effective against contracting zoonosis. This was in contrast to earlier findings from a study in Ebonyi State which showed that a much higher number had good hygiene practice.¹⁶ It was, however, similar to results documented by studies in Ogun, Ebonyi and Sokoto States which showed that low proportions of respondents had good practice towards prevention of zoonosis.^{12,17} Another study in South Africa also showed more than half of respondents to have good hygienic practices.¹⁴

The high level of knowledge in this study did not translate to consistent practice of effective preventive measures against zoonotic diseases.

The implication of the observed ineffective preventive practices cutting across all the socio-demographic characteristics of the study participants suggest the need for periodic training and retraining cutting across board. The training will as well aim at formation of better attitude since attitude is formed based on information available. Positive improvements in attitude can be achieved by improving appropriate and periodic information on zoonosis. These reports underscore the necessity of health education intervention in all preventive and control measures against zoonosis. The health education program should aim at increasing their level of knowledge, changing their beliefs and their attitude towards zoonosis and their practice of preventive measures.

This study generated results for policy makers in Ebonyi State Ministry of Health, Ebonyi State Ministry of Environment and Local Government Areas of Ebonyi State. The findings will contribute to formulating new food/meat safety policies and strengthening existing strategies in protecting abattoir workers as well as safeguarding consumers from zoonotic diseases. The data in this study were self-reported by abattoir workers which might have introduced some bias in their knowledge and risks of acquiring zoonotic diseases. This was controlled by discussing with them the consequences of inaccurate information to the study outcome. They were assured of absolute confidentiality of information provided and non-disclosure. The study was carried in Ebonyi North Senatorial District of Ebonyi State thus limits the extent to which the findings can be generalized to the wider population. Thus further studies should be done in all the Senatorial Districts of the State.

Conclusion

This study demonstrated a high level of knowledge of zoonotic diseases among abattoir workers in Ebonyi North Senatorial District. However, this did not commensurately translate to consistent practice of effective preventive measures against zoonotic diseases. We therefore recommend further health education, training and re-training of abattoir workers to enable them practice effective prevention measures and to

reduce the risk of contracting zoonosis.

Authors' contributions - BII conceptualized and designed the study. BII, TCC, FIO, POE, MIE, NUN and ECA collected the data. BII and TCC analyzed and interpreted the data. BII, TCC, FIO, POE, NUN, MIE and ECA wrote the manuscript. All authors critically reviewed and approved the final draft of the manuscript.

Disclosure

Conflict of interest: None

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